

EXCEL REPORTING TOOLS FOR GENERATING XML FILES

Guidelines for reporting Pesticide residues to EFSA according to Regulation (EC) No 396/2005

1. INTRODUCTION

The Excel reporting tools are Excel files specifically customized to support the data providers for compiling and reporting pesticide residues data to EFSA. In particular, they generate the XML Files with the correct structure for transmission to EFSA via the DCF (Data Collection Framework) and in line with the [SSD1](#)¹ or [SSD2](#)² (Standard Sample Description 1 and 2) data model.

1.1. XML files

XML (Extensible Markup Language) is the data format required to submit structured data to the EFSA Data Collection Framework.

All the technical details and specifications for the preparation of valid XML files for the DCF are contained in *The Guidance on Data Exchange version 2.0* (<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2014.3945>).

1.2. SSD2

The *Chemical Monitoring Reporting Guideline* ([DOI 10.5281/zenodo.2543210](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2543210)) provides the general specification on how to follow the SSD2 data model for a harmonized data reporting of Chemical Contaminants, Pesticides, Additives and Veterinary Medicinal Product Residues.

A more detailed description of the SSD2 data model is contained in the original guidance *Standard Sample Description ver. 2.0* (<https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.2903/j.efsa.2013.3424>)

Specific guidelines for the pesticides monitoring data collection (MOPER) are given in the working instructions³ distributed to the data providers as a complement to the main guideline.

1.3. SSD1

The document *Standard sample description for food and feed* (<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2010.1457>) is the first release (SSD1) of general specifications for reporting occurrence data of Chemical Contaminants in food and feed, (including Pesticides).

Every year a specific SSD1 guidance for reporting pesticides data was published. The last specific SSD1 guidance is in use for the MOPER2018 and will not be updated anymore because the SSD1 data transmission will be dismissed starting from the 2019 data collection. *Reporting data on pesticide residues in food and feed according to Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 (2018 data collection)* (<https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.2903/j.efsa.2019.5655>)

¹ [Standard sample description for food and feed](#) (EFSA, 2010)

² [Standard Sample Description ver. 2.0](#) (EFSA, 2013)

³ SSD2 coding of the food and feed samples tested in the frame of the pesticide residue monitoring under Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 and their analytical results

2. THE TOOLS

Four Excel tools for XML creation with pesticides monitoring data are currently available:

- Excel tool FLAT for SSD1 data collection (will be dismissed after MOPER2018)
- Excel tool FLAT for SSD2 data collection
- Excel tool With Methods for SSD1 data collection (will be dismissed after MOPER2018)
- Excel tool With Methods for SSD2 data collection

Considering that the SSD1 tools will be dismissed after the MOPER2018 data collection and that the structure and mechanisms of the SSD1 and SSD2 tools are analogous, this guidance is mainly focused on the SSD2 tools.

The main items of the tools enabling the users to create valid XML files are:

- SSD mandatory fields already set as worksheet headers.
- Extended comments on each header of the SSD2 tools giving compilation instructions and cross-referencing the SSD1-SSD2 variable names for an easier migration to the SSD2 data model.
- Data validation on all the variables for which a controlled terminology exists. Each of these cells can be filled in selecting elements from a picking list where only the reportable terms are available according to reportability constraints set in the catalogues and in the specific guidelines.
- Formulas for the retrieval of *paramCode* by selecting the names of substances from a specific picking list.
- Formulas for generating the unique result identifier (*resultCode* in SSD1 and *resId* in SSD2)
- Formulas for the retrieval of *prodCode* in SSD1 by selecting the names of food in the specific picking list

3. GETTING STARTED

Once downloaded the tool, please save it locally on your computer before opening it.

The first time the tool is opened a warning message of “Protected View” can appear on the top of the worksheet as in Figure 1. If this happens, please click on the “Enable editing” button.

Figure 1: Steps to enable editing

Continuing to open the tool a second security warning notifies that macros have been disabled. Please select the ‘enable macros’ option following the steps as seen in Figure 2.

If the macro are not enabled the tool cannot create the XML output file.

Figure 2: Steps to enable the macros

4. THE WORKBOOKS

Two types of workbook are available as XML creation tools: the XML creation tool FLAT and WITH METHODS. The structure and usage of the tools is different even if both of them are aimed to produce the same output: a valid XML file ready for submission in DCF. The FLAT tool is conceived for a simpler usage without structuring the input data. Some information describing samples and analytical scope is redundant in this tool. The tool WITH METHODS allows to reduce redundancies provided that input data are appropriately structured.

4.1. The XML creation tool “FLAT”

The FLAT tool is implemented as a simple Excel table with the mandatory SSD variables in the columns and as many records as the analytical results reported. Each record has to be filled in with all the information related to a single analytical result. The information related to the sample descriptors has to be repeated identically for all the results belonging to the same sample. The laboratory parameters referred to a substance have to be repeated for each sample where the same analytical scope applies.

The FLAT tool consists of two worksheets:

RUN_XML_CREATION: The worksheet contains a button to run the code that automatically generates the XML file.

Samples: The worksheet is used for the compilation of data describing the samples and all the analytical results related to each. The data provider should follow the proposed structure to get a valid XML. Modifications to the variable names in the column headers will prevent the creation of a valid XML. The insertion of new columns is allowed provided that the correct SSD field name is put in the new headers. Elimination of columns is also allowed, provided that mandatory fields are all retained.

Figure 3: The two spreadsheets of the FLAT tool

4.2. The XML creation tool “WITH METHODS”

The tool WITH METHODS is implemented as a set of Excel tables aiming at the reduction of data input by the data provider minimizing redundant information. The sample descriptors are repeated once for each analytical method applied to the sample. The laboratory parameters of an analytical method are compiled only once in the related *Method* worksheet. The information related to analytical results is summarized in the *Results* worksheet that contains only positive detections with occurrence quantification, legal limits and evaluation of the results. The result evaluation of non-detections is set to “below the MRL” by default when the XML file is generated.

The tool WITH METHODS consists of four worksheets:

RUN_XML_CREATION: this worksheet contains a button that runs the code that automatically generates the XML file.

Samples: all the samples reported are listed and described in this worksheet with a unique sample identifier and all the sample descriptors according to the SSD data model. The last column of this worksheet (“MethodSheet”) is not an SSD field, but contains the Method names referred to the Method sheet where the analytical scope for that sample is reported. The records with the sample information are repeated for the same sample as many times as the number of analytical methods that apply to that sample.

Methods: The tool WITH METHODS is provided with an empty Method worksheet (named “Method1”). The data provider needs to make a multiple copy of the worksheet ‘Method1’ according to the amount of analysis methods used and rename the worksheets with a method name. There are no constraints for the names of the Method worksheets. The data provider is free to decide the method name, provided that it is reported consistently (identical) in the column “MethodSheet” of the Samples worksheet. The compilation of data in these worksheets needs to be specific to the method mentioned.

Please note that specifying the analysis parameters in one of the Method sheets is mandatory for all the substances analysed, either if non-detected or positive results.

Results: The worksheet is used for the compilation of data stating the results and the evaluation. The Results worksheet contains only positive detections with occurrence quantification, legal limits and evaluation of the results. The result evaluation of non-detections (not listed in the Results worksheet) is set to “below the MRL” by default when the XML file is generated. The data provider should follow the structure to enable the export to XML.

Please note that a positive detection cannot be present in the Results worksheet only, but the related laboratory parameters have to be specified also in one of the Method sheets. Otherwise the XML output will not contain the substance analysed.

Figure 4: The four spreadsheet types of the WITH METHODS tool

4.3. Data elements

The SSD2 data model for reporting pesticide residues data includes several data elements. Detailed explanations on the different data elements are provided in the Chemical Monitoring Reporting Guideline (SSD2) and the specific working instructions for pesticide residues reporting.

Additionally, the comments in each header of the SSD2 XML creation tools provide a quick reference to the SSD2 data elements. In both type of tools only the SSD data elements considered relevant for the Pesticides data collection are included (mandatory data elements and few more, either in the SSD2 or the SSD1 tools).

Examples of data elements to report for each spreadsheet are provided in the figures below.

progId	progLegalRef	sampStrategy	progType	sampMethod	sampler	sampPoint	sampEventId	sampUnitType	sampId
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Figure 5: Example of data elements in the 'samples' worksheet

analysisY	paramType	paramCode	paramText	anMethRefId	anMethType
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Figure 6: Example of data elements in the 'Method' worksheet

sampId	paramCode	paramText	resId	resVal	resValRec
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Figure 7: Example of data elements in the 'Results' worksheet

The definition of each data element is provided in the SSD2 Flat and With Method tools by placing the mouse over the element name. A comment will pop-out that indicates the name of the controlled terminology (catalogue of SSD2 valid terms for the specific data element), and refers to the SSD1 data element name if it existed. In some cases, the different codes that can be transmitted are listed, or the note specifies the reference guidance to the data provider. It is also mentioned if the reporting is mandatory or optional.

progLegalRef	sampStrategy	pr	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SSD2 Code: B.03 - SSD2 Element: sampStrategy - Description: Sampling strategy - Controlled Terminology: SAMPSTR - Reporting is: Mandatory for the MOPER data collection - In SSD1 it was: progSampStrategy - Operational notes: For pesticides one of the following codes should be reported: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ST10A - Objective sampling ST20A - Selective sampling ST30A - Suspect sampling 	sam
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Figure 8: Data element description in SSD2 tools

5. Completing the worksheet

A list of reportable codes is provided for all the data elements for which an SSD controlled terminology exists. The list of codes is provided in the tool as a picking list with the aim to support the data input and to provide a first data validation control. However, in all the cases where a controlled terminology doesn't exist the data provider must enter the code manually.

proglid	progLegalRef	sampStrategy	progType
	<input type="text" value=""/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> N018A N027A N028A N247A 		

Figure 9: Selection of data element codes

In the Flat and With Methods tools, the formula to retrieve the *paramCode* and to calculate the *resId* is already created. The code will be automatically mapped and entered by selecting the appropriate *paramText*.

In both SSD1 tools, there are formulae for the retrieval of *prodCode* by selecting the names of food (*prodText*) from a specific picking list.

paramType	paramCode	paramText	anMethRefId
	RF-0004-001-PPP	<input type="text" value="1,3-dichloropropene"/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1,3-dichloropropene 1,4-Dimethylnaphthalene 1-methylcyclopropene 1-naphthylacetamide 1-Naphthylacetamide and 1-naphthyl: 1-naphthylacetic acid 2-(4-Hydroxyanilino)-4,6-dimethylpyr 2,2,2-Trichloro-1-(3,4-dichloropheny 	

Figure 10: Selection of the *paramCode* in the 'Method' worksheet

In case a different element is provided than the one listed in *paramText*, the *paramCode* will not be automatically mapped and an error message will indicate that the value is not valid. Therefore, it is important for the data provider to enter the correct name or to select the element in the list. In the example below (Figure 11), the valid *paramText* found in the list would be '1,3-dichloropropene'.

paramType	paramCode	paramText	anMethRefId
		<input type="text" value="dichloropropene"/>	

Microsoft Excel

The value you entered is not valid.

A user has restricted values that can be entered into this cell.

Figure 11: Mapping of *paramCode* to *paramText*

6. Creation of the XML

Once the data table is completed and ready for transferring the data to the XML file, the data provider must click the grey button in the **Run_XML_Creation** worksheet and select 'yes' to confirm the XML creation.

Figure 12: Creation of the XML file

If the XML file is successfully created, the message below should appear.

Figure 13: Validation of the XML file creation

If needed, the Excel tool automatically splits the dataset inserted in the workbooks and creates XML files of suitable size for the upload to the DCF (i.e. max 20.000 records per file). If only one XML is created it is named by default 'AnalyticalMeasure1' and saved following the path of the Excel tool location (also indicated in the Excel Info page, **Figure 14**).

If more than one XML are generated (due to the high number of records) the next output files will have all the same name, followed by a progressive numbering (e.g. 'AnalyticalMeasure1', 'AnalyticalMeasure2', 'AnalyticalMeasure3', etc.)

For this reason it is suggested to modify the default names of the XML files with more meaningful names, possibly referred to the content of the file.

Figure 14: Path to the XML file